

Farmers' Knowledge, Post-harvest Practices, and their Impact on Fungal Contamination and Seed Viability of Maize (*Zea mays* L.) in Ethiopia

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Authors' contributions

This work was carried out in collaboration between both authors. Both authors read and approved the final manuscript.

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Abstract

Maize is the most important cereal crop in Ethiopia, but post-harvest fungal contamination threatens food safety and seed viability. This study aimed to assess smallholder farmers' knowledge of mycotoxins, their pre- and post-harvest practices, and the consequent impact on fungal load and seed viability. A cross sectional survey was conducted among 60 farmers in four major maize producing districts (Bako Tibe, Ilu Gala, Boricha, and Halaba). 180 maize grain samples were collected at three stages: at harvest, after three months of farm storage, and after six months from local markets. Using the standard blotter method, kernel infection, germination percentage, vigour index, and fungal genera were determined. The survey revealed profound knowledge gaps: 91.7% of farmers had never heard of aflatoxins or fumonisins, 95.0% were unaware of associated health risks, and 100% attributed mould solely to storage pests. Hazardous practices were common: 100% used traditional maturity tests (biting), 51.7% delayed harvest, 80% used manual threshing, 75% did not dry grain, and only 10% used hermetic PICS bags. Kernel infection increased significantly ($p \leq 0.05$)

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from 87.2% at harvest to 99.1% in market samples. *Fusarium* was the dominant genus, increasing from 48.7% to 78.4% along the value chain. Germination collapsed from 82% (field) to 46% (market), and vigour index became immeasurable in market samples. The combination of poor knowledge and hazardous practices creates conditions that favour fungal proliferation and destroy seed viability. Urgent interventions awareness campaigns, hermetic storage, moisture-based harvest decisions, and resistant varieties are required.

Keywords: *Fusarium, germination, kernel infection, maize, mycotoxin awareness, post-harvest practices, seed viability, Ethiopia.*

1. Introduction

Maize (*Zea mays* L.) is the most important cereal crop in Ethiopia in terms of total grain production and productivity, and it is the primary staple for the majority of Ethiopian households (CSA, 2021). Approximately 88% of the produce is consumed directly on-farm, making maize a cornerstone of national food security. Despite significant yield gains over the past two decades, namely from 1.6 t ha⁻¹ in the 1990s to over 4.2 t ha⁻¹ recently, productivity remains well below the global average of 5.6 t ha⁻¹, largely due to post-harvest losses and fungal contamination (FAO, 2019; Abate et al., 2015).

Fungal pathogens, particularly *Fusarium*, *Aspergillus*, and *Penicillium* species, are the primary agents of maize grain deterioration in Ethiopia (Getachew et al., 2018; Ayalew, 2010). These fungi invade grain in the field and during storage, causing kernel discoloration, nutritional losses, and reduced seed viability (Munkvold, 2017). More importantly, they produce toxic secondary metabolites (mycotoxins), including fumonisins and aflatoxins, which pose serious risks to human and animal health (Wild & Gong, 2010; Marasas et al., 2004). In Ethiopia, Getachew et al. (2018) detected 127 different mycotoxins in stored maize, with fumonisin B₁ concentrations reaching up to 11,830 µg kg⁻¹, far exceeding EU limits. Chronic exposure to aflatoxins is linked to hepatocellular carcinoma, immune suppression, and childhood stunting, while fumonisins are associated with esophageal cancer and neural tube defects (IARC, 2012; Missmer et al., 2006).

Mycotoxin contamination is strongly exacerbated by poor pre- and post-harvest practices. Most smallholder farmers in Ethiopia determine harvest maturity using traditional methods such as visual inspection or the "biting test", and delayed harvesting is common, allowing *Fusarium* to move from the silk channel into the kernels (Abate et al., 2020). Manual threshing, namely by beating sacks or cobs with sticks, causes mechanical damage to the pericarp, creating entry points for storage fungi. After harvest, the majority of farmers store shelled maize in traditional porous structures such as the Gotera or Gombisa, which are woven granaries made of bamboo, wood and mud. These structures allow moisture ingress and create microclimates conducive to fungal growth (Tefera et al., 2011). Although many farmers apply insecticides to control storage pests, the lack of hermetic structures means that surviving insects produce metabolic water, raising local humidity and actually promoting fungal proliferation even when chemical products are used (Mubayiwa et al., 2021; Williams et al., 2014). Consequently, kernel infection rates increase progressively from harvest to storage to market, and seed viability declines dramatically. Fungal invasion depletes endosperm reserves and damages the embryo, leading to poor germination and low seedling vigour (Munkvold, 2017). In a system where many farmers rely on saved seed or market-purchased grain for the next planting season, this loss of viability perpetuates a cycle of low productivity and food insecurity.

A critical barrier to effective mycotoxin management is the low level of awareness among farmers. Studies from across sub-Saharan Africa have shown that although farmers can visually identify mouldy grain, the vast majority have never heard of "aflatoxin" or "fumonisin" and do not associate mouldy food with chronic diseases such as liver cancer (James et al., 2020). In Ethiopia, Biru and Genta (2022) reported very low knowledge of fungal and mycotoxin contamination among respondents in Oromia, and Tadesse et al. (2025) found that only 29% of farmers in Northwest Ethiopia had good knowledge of mycotoxins, with educational status being the strongest predictor. Nevertheless, most previous studies have either focused exclusively on mycotoxin detection in stored grain or assessed farmer knowledge in isolation. They have not simultaneously linked varietal preference, post-harvest handling practices and farmer awareness to the biological outcomes of fungal load and seed viability along the entire value chain, specifically from harvest through storage to market. This integrated perspective is essential for identifying the most effective intervention points. Therefore, the present study was

designed to: (i) evaluate farmers' awareness of mycotoxins and their health risks; (ii) characterise current pre- and post-harvest management practices; (iii) determine the cumulative effect of these practices on fungal contamination, seed germination and vigour along the value chain; and (iv) identify critical intervention points for improving maize seed quality and food safety.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Study Areas

The study was conducted in four districts purposively selected from three major maize producing regions of Ethiopia: Bako Tibe and Ilu Galan from West Shewa Zone (Oromia Regional State), Boricha and Halaba from the Sidama and Central Ethiopia Regional States (formerly part of the Southern Nations, Nationalities and Peoples' Region). These districts were chosen because they are important maize growing areas with contrasting agro ecological conditions, ranging from high rainfall mid altitude zones (Bako Tibe, Ilu Gala) to drier Rift Valley lowlands (Boricha, Halaba). The selection was based on maize production potential, accessibility, and the prevalence of traditional storage practices (Fig. 1).

Bako Tibe (09°07'33" N, 37°03'75" E; altitude 1,900–2,060 m a.s.l.) and Ilu Galan (08°59'51" N, 37°19'49" E; altitude 1,900–2,060 m a.s.l.) are located in the western Ethiopian highlands. They receive unimodal rainfall from June to October, with mean annual precipitation ranging from 1,300 to 1,400 mm and average maximum temperatures of 28 °C. The climate is warm and humid, which favours high maize productivity. Soils are mainly Nitisols and Vertisols.

Boricha (06°54'90" N, 38°20'40" E; altitude 1,820 m a.s.l.) and Halaba (07°19'04" N, 38°04'90" E; altitude 1,820 m a.s.l.) are situated in the Ethiopian Rift Valley. They have a bimodal rainfall pattern, with small rains from March to May and main rains from June to September. Annual precipitation totals 1,000–1,200 mm, and maximum temperatures range from 23 to 31 °C. These districts are warmer and drier. Soils include Andosols, Fluvisols, Vertisols and Regosols. Maize is grown under both rain-fed and small-scale irrigation, and storage is often in *Gotera*, underground pits, or sacks. Harvesting takes place from November to December, when average temperature and precipitation are at their lowest.

Table 1. Geographic description (altitude, coordinates, rainfall and temperature) of the four study districts in Ethiopia

District	Altitude (m a.s.l.)	Latitude (N)	Longitude (E)	Mean annual RF (mm)	Max. Temp (°C)
Boricha	1820	06°54'90"	038°20'40"	1000	25
Halaba	1820	07°19'04"	038°04'90"	1200	23
Bako Tibe	2060	09°07'33"	037°03'75"	1300	28
Ilu Galan	1900	08°59'51"	037°19'49"	1400	28

Table 2. Meteorological data (2019 and 2020) for the study districts obtained from the national meteorology agency of Ethiopia (Adama and Hawassa branches)

District	Year	Av. max T (°C)	Av. min T (°C)	Com. Av. T (°C)	Av. RF (mm)	Av. RH (%)
Boricha	2019	28.8	14.5	21.7	79.7	NA
	2020	29.1	14.9	22.0	110.0	NA
Halaba	2019	29.1	14.6	21.9	215.8	NA
	2020	30.7	15.2	23.0	230.6	NA
Bako Tibe	2019	29.7	14.8	22.3	94.1	NA
	2020	30.6	15.3	23.0	74.6	NA
Ilu Gala	2019	28.9	13.7	21.3	114.9	62.1
	2020	28.2	13.6	20.9	141.7	63.5

NA = not available; RF = rainfall; RH = relative humidity; Com. Av. T = combined average temperature

Fig. 1. Map of Ethiopia depicting the study areas

Meteorological data for the 2019 and 2020 cropping seasons were obtained from the National Meteorology Agency of Ethiopia (Adama and Hawassa branches). The combined average temperature across districts ranged from 20.9 to 23.0 °C, and relative humidity (where recorded) was 62–64%. Detailed geographical coordinates and climatic characteristics are presented in Table 1 and Table 2.

2.2 Survey and Sample Collection

A total of 60 maize producing households (15 per district, from three kebeles per district) were randomly selected. A pre-tested semi structured questionnaire was administered face-to-face in local languages (Afaan Oromo, Sidama Afoo, Amharic) to collect data on socio-demographics, varietal preference, harvest and post-harvest practices, and awareness of mycotoxins.

In addition, 180 maize grain samples (500 g each) were collected at three-time points: from fields immediately after harvest (n=60), from farmers' storage structures after three months (n=60), and from local open markets

after six months (n=60). Samples were transported in sterile paper bags to the Plant Pathology Laboratory of Hawassa Agricultural Research Center and stored at 4°C until analysis.

2.3 Blotter Method for Mycological Analysis and Seed Viability

The standard blotter method was used following ISTA guidelines (ISTA, 2019). Qualitative Whatman No. 1 filter paper (150 mm diameter) was sterilized in a dry oven at 180°C for 30 minutes. For each sample, 20 kernels were randomly selected; surface sterilized with 1% sodium hypochlorite for 1 minute, rinsed three times with sterile distilled water, and aseptically placed on moist filter paper in 15 cm diameter Petri dishes. Three replications were prepared per sample (total 60 kernels per sample). Plates were incubated at 25±2°C under 12 h near ultraviolet light/12 h darkness for 7 days.

After 7 days, kernel infection (%) was calculated as (number of seeds with visible fungal growth / total seeds) × 100. Germination percentage (%) was calculated as (number of seeds producing normal seedlings – defined as radicle ≥2 cm and healthy coleoptiles divided by total seeds) × 100. Vigour index was calculated as germination percentage × mean seedling length (root + shoot, cm), following the method of Abdul-Baki and Anderson, (1973).

Moisture content determination: Grain moisture content was determined using the standard oven-drying method (ISO 712:2009). For each sample, 5 g of whole maize kernels were weighed into pre-dried aluminum dishes and dried in a forced-air oven at 130°C for 2 hours. Moisture content (%) was calculated as (initial weight – dry weight) / initial weight × 100. Measurements were performed in triplicate.

Fungal colonies were examined under a stereo binocular microscope and a compound microscope (40×). Identification to genus level was based on colony colour, texture, mycelial characteristics, conidial shape and arrangement, and conidiophore morphology, following standard identification keys (Leslie and Summerell, 2006). Frequency of each genus (%) was calculated as (number of samples in which the genus was detected / total number of samples) × 100.

2.4 Statistical Analysis

Survey data were analyzed using SPSS version 23 (descriptive statistics, frequencies). Biological data (kernel infection, germination, vigour) were subjected to analysis of variance (ANOVA) using SAS version 9.2, and means were separated by Fisher's least significant difference (LSD) test at $p \leq 0.05$.

3. Results

3.1 Socio Demographic Characteristics and Mycotoxin Awareness of Farmers

The survey of 60 farmers revealed that 80% were male and 70% were aged between 20 and 40 years. Nearly 39% had no formal education, while 41% had primary education, 12% secondary, and only 8% tertiary education. The majority (73.3%) cultivated the older maize variety 'Limu', followed by BH-147 (13.3%), local varieties (6.7%), Shone (5.0%), and only 1.7% used the improved hybrid BH-540. Although 76.7% of farmers had heard about mould, 91.7% had never heard of aflatoxins or fumonisins, and 95.0% were unaware of the associated health risks. Only 5.0% knew that mouldy grain could cause health problems, and 10.0% were aware that mould might cause cancer. All farmers (100%) attributed mould solely to storage pests, and none (0%) identified fungi as the causal agent. When asked about mould colour observed on stored grain, 45% reported black mould, 25% brown or yellow, 15% red, and 15% white (Table 3).

3.2 Pre- and Post-harvest Management Practices

All 60 farmers (100%) used traditional methods (visual inspection or biting test) to determine harvest maturity, and none used moisture testing equipment. Crop rotation was practiced by 68.3% of farmers. Delayed harvest was practiced by 51.7% of farmers, with 38.3% leaving grain in the field for up to one month and 33.3% for two to three weeks; only 28.3% harvested as soon as the crop matured. Sorting of damaged kernels during harvest was done by only 25.0% of farmers. Manual threshing (beating sacks or cobs with sticks) was used by 80.0%, while only 20.0% used mechanical shelling. Only 30.0% of farmers dried grain after harvest, and of those who dried, 75.0% dried on bare ground. Regarding storage structures, 45.0% used traditional *Gotera* (woven

granary), 11.7% used sacks, 33.3% used a combination of *Gotera* and sacks, and only 10.0% used hermetic PICS bags. Insecticides were applied by 86.7% of farmers. Storage location was inside the house for 55.0% and in the courtyard for 45.0%. Clean storage structures were reported by 76.7% of farmers (Table 4).

Table 3. Socio-demographic characteristics and mycotoxin awareness of smallholder maize farmers (N=60)

Variable	Category	N (%)	Variable	Category	N (%)
Age	20–40	42 (70.0)	Heard about aflatoxin/fumonisin?	Yes	5 (8.3)
	41–60	13 (21.7)		No	55 (91.7)
	>60	5 (8.3)			
Sex	Male	48 (80.0)	Aware of health risks?	Yes	3 (5.0)
	Female	12 (20.0)		No	57 (95.0)
Education	None	23 (38.7)	Primary cause of mould?	Storage pests	60 (100.0)
	Primary	25 (41.3)		Poor drying	34 (56.7)
	Secondary	7 (11.7)		Lack of cleaning	17 (28.3)
	Tertiary	5 (8.3)	Aware mould causes cancer?	Yes	6 (10.0)
Maize variety	Limu	44 (73.3)	Aware causal agent (fungi)?	No	54 (90.0)
	BH-147	8 (13.3)		Yes	0 (0.0)
	Local	4 (6.7)	Mould colour observed	No	60 (100.0)
	Shone	3 (5.0)		Black	27 (45.0)
	BH-540	1 (1.7)		Brown/yellow	15 (25.0)
Heard about mould?	Yes	46 (76.7)	Red	9 (15.0)	
	No	14 (23.3)	White	9 (15.0)	

Table 4. Pre- and post-harvest management practices of maize among smallholder farmers (N=60)

Practice	Response	N (%)	Practice	Response	N (%)
Crop rotation	Yes	41 (68.3)	Drying after harvest	Yes	18 (30.0)
	No	19 (31.7)		No	42 (70.0)
Harvest as soon as mature	Yes	29 (48.3)	Storage structure	Gotera	27 (45.0)
	No	31 (51.7)		PICS bag	6 (10.0)
Maturity method	Traditional	60 (100.0)		Sacks	7 (11.7)
	Moisture test	0 (0.0)	Gotera+sacks	20 (33.3)	
Field storage duration	1 month	23 (38.3)	Insecticide use	Yes	52 (86.7)
	2–3 weeks	20 (33.3)		No	8 (13.3)
	None	17 (28.3)	Storage location	In house	33 (55.0)
Sorting during harvest	Yes	15 (25.0)		Courtyard	27 (45.0)
	No	45 (75.0)	Clean storage structure	Yes	46 (76.7)
Threshing method	Manual	48 (80.0)		No	14 (23.3)
		Mechanical	12 (20.0)		

3.3 Kernel Infection, Germination and Vigour Index

Grain moisture content varied significantly along the value chain ($p \leq 0.05$). Mean moisture content was 21.7% at harvest (field samples), which decreased to 12.0% after three months of farm storage, but then increased again to 13.2% in market samples after six months ($LSD = 1.8$, $p \leq 0.05$). This U-shaped trend indicates that grain rewetting occurs during market storage.

Kernel infection increased significantly along the value chain ($p \leq 0.05$). At harvest (field samples), mean kernel infection was 87.2%, rising to 92.8% after three months of farm storage and reaching 99.1% after six months in local markets. Among districts, kernel infection averaged 95.8% in Bako Tibe, 94.3% in Ilu Gala, 92.8% in Boricha, and 89.4% in Halaba. Halaba had significantly lower infection than the other three districts (Table 5). Germination percentage declined sharply from field to market, with the highest germination (82%) recorded in Halaba field samples and the lowest (46%) in Boricha market samples. The vigour index fell from 436.1

(Halaba field) to 141.6 (Boricha storage) and became immeasurable in all market samples due to insufficient seedling growth (Table 6). The decline in germination is illustrated in Fig. 2.

Table 5. Kernel infection (%) of maize grain on blotter method by sample source and district

Sample source	N	Kernel infection (%)
Market (6 months)	60	99.1 a
Storage (3 months)	60	92.8 b
Field (harvest)	60	87.2 c
Mean		93.0
LSD ($p \leq 0.05$)		1.11
District		
Bako Tibe	45	95.8 a
Ilu Galan	45	94.3 a
Boricha	45	92.8 a
Halaba	45	89.4 b
Mean		93.1
LSD ($p \leq 0.05$)		1.7

Means followed by the same letter within a column are not significantly different ($\alpha = 0.05$)

Fig. 2. Blotter method incubation for maize kernel infections. Description: A and B: Ungerminated seed and colonized by *Aspergillus*, *Fusarium* and *Penicillium* species; C and D: Healthy and germinated seed

Table 6. Germination percentage (G %), vigour index (VI), and kernel infection (KI %) of maize grain on blotter method by district and sample source

District	Sample source	G%	VI	KI%
Boricha	Field	70	330.6	90
	Storage	53	141.6	90
	Market	46	NA	100
Halaba	Field	82	436.1	75
	Storage	76	352.7	94
	Market	64	NA	100
Ilu Galan	Field	67	344.4	94
	Storage	63	216.6	94
	Market	54	NA	100
Bako Tibe	Field	71	391.3	90
	Storage	67	256.7	93
	Market	62	NA	100

NA = not available (seedling growth insufficient for vigour index calculation)

3.4 Fungal Genera Isolated and Seed Health Outcomes

The blotter method incubation revealed clear visual differences between healthy and infected seeds (Fig. 2). Ungerminated seeds were heavily colonized by *Aspergillus*, *Fusarium* and *Penicillium* species, while healthy seeds germinated normally.

Table 7. Frequency percentage of *Fusarium* and *Aspergillus* genera on blotter method by sample source and districts in 2019 /2020 cropping season

Sample source	District	<i>Fusarium</i> (%)	<i>Aspergillus</i> (%)	Other genera (%)
Field	Boricha	44.0	15.6	40.4
	Halaba	67.5	23.3	9.2
	Bako Tibe	39.9	11.1	49.0
	Ilu Gala	43.2	11.0	45.8
	Mean	48.7	15.3	36.0
Storage	Boricha	69.2	11.7	19.1
	Halaba	76.7	13.3	10.0
	Bako Tibe	77.2	12.2	10.6
	Ilu Gala	53.3	20.0	26.7
	Mean	69.1	14.3	16.6
Market	Boricha	91.0	8.5	0.5
	Halaba	85.0	9.5	5.5
	Bako Tibe	64.0	46.0	10.0
	Ilu Gala	74.0	13.0	13.0
	Mean	78.4	19.3	2.3

Fifteen fungal genera were isolated, with the major toxigenic genera being *Fusarium*, *Aspergillus* and *Penicillium*. Other genera included *Rhizopus*, yeast, *Trichoderma*, *Mucor*, *Nigrospora*, *Epicoccum*, *Chaetomium*, and *Curvularia* (rare). The frequency of *Fusarium* increased progressively from 48.7% at harvest to 69.1% after three months of storage and to 78.4% in market samples. *Aspergillus* frequency was 15.3% at harvest, 14.3% after storage, and 19.3% in markets, with a peak of 46.0% in Bako Tibe market samples. Because a single sample may contain multiple genera, frequencies are not mutually exclusive; column sums may exceed 100% (Table 7).

4. Discussion

The present study revealed a profound knowledge deficit among Ethiopian smallholder maize farmers, with only 8.3% having ever heard of aflatoxins or fumonisins, 95.0% unaware of associated health risks, and all farmers (100%) attributing mould solely to storage pests (Table 3). These findings are strikingly consistent with reports

from across sub-Saharan Africa. In Tanzania, Magembe et al. (2016) found that 97% of farmers were unaware of mycotoxins, and a recent study reported that 95.4% of smallholder farmers had no knowledge of aflatoxin biocontrol technologies (Fundikira et al., 2024). A systematic review from Malawi documented an average mycotoxin awareness level of only 24.5% among farmers, traders and workers, with no measurable improvements in knowledge, attitudes and practices indicators between 2012 and 2025 (Chilaka et al., 2017). In southern Mozambique, Siteo et al. (2025) reported that 97.8% of farmers had insufficient knowledge about fungi and mycotoxin contamination, and most, including those affected by liver cancer, showed limited understanding of the connection between mouldy food and health issues. Similarly, in Ethiopia, Biru and Genta (2022) found very low knowledge of fungal and mycotoxin contamination among respondents in Oromia, and Tadesse et al. (2025) reported that only 29% of farmers in Northwest Ethiopia had good knowledge of mycotoxins, with educational status being the strongest predictor. The misattribution of mould solely to pests in the present study directs farmers' efforts toward insecticidal control while neglecting moisture management, a critical oversight, as moisture is the primary driver of fungal growth (Abate et al., 2015; Hell and Mutegi, 2011; Williams et al., 2014).

The hazardous practices documented in this study were near universal (Table 4). All farmers used traditional maturity tests (biting or visual inspection), and none used moisture testing equipment, a finding mirrored in Tanzania (Magembe et al., 2016), Ghana (Akowuah et al., 2015), Guatemala (Mendoza et al., 2018) and Ethiopia (Abate et al., 2015). The biting test is particularly problematic as it introduces saliva, providing moisture and microbial inoculum (Hell and Mutegi, 2011; Kaaya et al., 2005). Over half of the farmers (51.7%) delayed harvest, with 38.3% leaving grain in the field for up to one month. This practice of temporary field storage has been shown to allow *Fusarium* to move from the silk channel into the kernels, increasing fumonisin contamination (Abate et al., 2015; Hell and Mutegi, 2011; Kaaya et al., 2005). Manual threshing (80% of farmers) causes micro-fissures in the pericarp that serve as entry pathways for storage fungi. Fandohan et al. (2003, 2006) demonstrated that mechanical shelling significantly reduced fungal infection and fumonisin levels compared to manual beating, with reductions of 57–65%. The high proportion of farmers who did not dry grain after harvest (70%) and those who dried on bare ground (75% of dryers) further exacerbates contamination, as bare ground is a primary source of *Fusarium* inoculum (Kaaya et al., 2005; Munkvold, 2017; Hell and Mutegi, 2011).

Storage practices were equally problematic: only 10% of farmers used hermetic PICS bags, while 45% used porous Gotera, 11.7% used sacks, and 33.3% used combinations (Table 4). Traditional structures in Ethiopia are strongly influenced by external climatic conditions, making grain liable to develop mould during the rainy season (Tefera et al., 2011). A previous study found that fungal incidence and frequency significantly increased with storage period ($p < 0.05$), with traditional structures providing less protection than hermetic alternatives. Monitoring inside traditional stores in Jimma Zone showed that all storage types were favourable for the growth of *Aspergillus*, *Fusarium* and *Penicillium* species, with a highly significant relationship between inside and outside temperature and humidity ($p < 0.001$). The moisture content data from the present study – 21.7% at harvest, 12.0% after three months of storage, but rising again to 13.2% in market samples – reveal a dangerous U-shaped trend (Table 6). Moisture above 13% allows dormant fungal spores to reactivate and grow (Williams et al., 2014; Kaaya et al., 2005). The rewetting phenomenon in markets is consistent with findings that moisture content increases after four months of storage due to respiration of grain and other organisms (Getachew et al., 2018).

Despite 86.7% of farmers using insecticides, kernel infection increased significantly ($p \leq 0.05$) from 87.2% at harvest to 99.1% in market samples (Table 5). The metabolic water produced by surviving insects in porous structures, as demonstrated by Chigoverah and Mvumi (2016) and Mubayiwa et al. (2021), explains this paradox. Walker et al. (2018) conducted a large-scale study in Kenya and found that hermetic storage significantly reduced the increase in fungal infection compared to polypropylene bags, with less than 5% per month increase in aflatoxin (a related outcome) achieved by metal silos and PICS bags. An earlier study showed that PICS bags prevented moisture penetration and the spread of fungi to non-infected kernels, whereas woven bags increased moisture and infection. Thus, chemical control alone in non-hermetic structures addresses the vector (insects) but fails to control the microclimate (moisture), rendering the intervention largely ineffective against fungal proliferation (Chigoverah and Mvumi, 2016; Williams et al., 2014).

Fusarium was the dominant genus isolated on blotter at all stages, increasing from 48.7% at harvest to 69.1% after three months and to 78.4% in market samples, with the highest frequency (91%) in Halaba market samples (Table 7). This dominance is consistent with multiple Ethiopian studies. Getachew et al. (2018) identified

Fusarium as the most frequent contaminant of stored maize, accounting for 70–100% of isolates. Tsehaye et al. (2017) reported that *Fusarium verticillioides* was the most prevalent species across 20 major maize growing areas, with isolation frequencies of 61–89%. Atnafu et al. (2024) found that *Fusarium* and *Penicillium* metabolites accounted for 27% and 30% of detected compounds in fresh harvests from southwestern Ethiopia. Deressa et al. (2024) surveyed 480 farmer fields across 10 Ethiopian zones and found that *Fusarium* ear rot severity was highest in West Wallaga, East Wallaga and Jimma zones, with strong associations between *Fusarium* incidence and poor agronomic practices. Hunde (2025) confirmed that the global increase in *Fusarium* species, particularly *F. verticillioides* in Ethiopia, demands urgent research attention, noting that ear rot and fungal contamination begin at the pre-harvest level. The high *Aspergillus* frequency observed in Bako Tibe market samples (46%) is also significant. *Aspergillus* species are known to thrive under warmer, drier conditions and have been frequently isolated from stored maize in Ethiopia (Ayalew, 2010). The co-occurrence of both *Fusarium* and *Aspergillus* in market samples indicates multiple fungal risks, which can lead to co-contamination by different classes of mycotoxins, as documented elsewhere in Africa (Wagacha and Muthomi, 2008; Hell and Mutegi, 2011).

The visual evidence from the blotter method (Fig. 2) clearly shows that fungi heavily colonized ungerminated seeds, while healthy seeds germinated normally. Seed germination collapsed from 82% (Halaba field) to 46% (Boricha market), resulting in a 36% absolute loss, and vigour index fell from 436.1 to 141.6, becoming immeasurable in market samples (Table 6, Fig. 2). This catastrophic decline has serious implications for farmers who rely on saved seed or market-purchased grain for the next planting season. Biemond et al. (2021) explained that seed-borne *Fusarium* species produce hydrolytic enzymes that degrade the embryo, leading to loss of viability. Tsedaley (2016) similarly found that heavily infected maize seeds showed only 40–50% germination compared to 85–90% in healthy seeds, a finding directly comparable to the present study's observations. Parikh et al. (2018) noted that seed vigour is the first component to suffer from fungal infection, leading to weak seedlings even if germination occurs. The strong inverse relationship between fungal infection and seed viability is consistent with seed health testing principles: the International Seed Testing Association (ISTA) recommends the blotter method precisely because incubation conditions that promote fungal growth simultaneously reveal the impact on germination (ISTA, 2019). The loss of vigour index in market samples indicates that even seeds that germinate produce weak seedlings with reduced radicle length and poor coleoptile development, leading to patchy stands, reduced yield and higher seeding rates, imposing hidden economic costs on smallholder farmers (Biemond et al., 2021).

The use of resistant or tolerant maize varieties is one of the most effective pre-harvest management strategies. An earlier finding evaluated commercial maize varieties in Ethiopia and found that while none were completely free of ear rot, Melkassa composite early maturing varieties (Melkassa 1, 4, and 7) exhibited significantly less severe disease than other hybrids, likely due to moisture and heat stress tolerance. Deressa et al. (2024) also reported that BH 661 and BH 540 showed moderate resistance compared to older hybrids. However, in the present study, 73.3% of farmers cultivated the commercial variety 'Limu', while only 1.7% used the improved hybrid BH 540 (Table 3). This is a major gap between research recommendations and farmer practice, also noted by Abate et al. (2020) and Keno et al. (2018). Agronomic practices also matter: Deressa et al. (2024) reported that high insect infestation, high weed density, low nitrogen fertilizer and low insecticide spraying frequency contributed to high *Fusarium* ear rot, while early planting, crop rotation and inter-cropping significantly reduced disease. These factors were reflected in the survey responses of the present study, where 68.3% practiced crop rotation, but only 48.3% harvested as soon as mature, and 86.7% applied insecticides while only 10% used hermetic storage (Table 4).

Several limitations of this study should be acknowledged. Species level identification of *Fusarium* and *Aspergillus* was not performed on blotter isolates, which would have required molecular or advanced morphological methods (e.g., carnation leaf agar) (Leslie and Summerell, 2006). Storage microclimate parameters (temperature, relative humidity within structures) were not continuously monitored, which could have provided mechanistic insights into moisture rewetting. The sample size (60 households, 180 samples) may not be fully representative of all Ethiopian maize growing zones. Finally, the cross-sectional design does not allow causal inference between specific practices and contamination outcomes, though the strong associations observed and consistency with longitudinal studies elsewhere (Deressa et al., 2024; Walker et al., 2018) support the conclusions.

Despite these limitations, the findings point to several clear intervention pathways. Farmer education must address the fundamental knowledge gap: distinguishing insects from fungi as causes of grain deterioration;

understanding that mouldy grain is hazardous even when insects are controlled; and recognizing that moisture management is critical (Sitoe et al., 2025; Tadesse et al., 2025). Sitoe et al. (2025) observed that commercial farmers in Mozambique demonstrated greater awareness due to market quality demands, suggesting that linking training to market incentives could improve adoption. Moisture management must be prioritized through provision of low-cost moisture meters to enable objective harvest timing ($\leq 18\%$ moisture) and drying to $\leq 13\%$ before storage (Kaaya et al., 2005; Hell and Mutegi, 2011). Hermetic storage technologies (PICS bags, metal silos) should be subsidized and promoted, but only in conjunction with proper drying, as storage of wet grain in hermetic conditions does not prevent fungal growth (Walker et al., 2018). Varietal improvement programmes should prioritize dissemination of resistant or tolerant hybrids (BH 540, BH 661, Melkassa composites) to replace the widely grown but susceptible 'Limu' (Deressa et al., 2024). Post-harvest processing interventions – namely mechanical shelling, sorting and drying on clean surfaces are should be promoted through extension services (Fandohan et al., 2006; Hell and Mutegi, 2011). Future research should integrate continuous monitoring of storage microclimate and evaluate the effectiveness of integrated intervention packages under randomized controlled trial conditions. The blotter method, as demonstrated in this study (Fig. 2), provides a simple, low cost, effective tool for routine seed health monitoring that can be deployed by extension services and farmer cooperatives to track grain quality and guide management decisions (ISTA, 2019; Tsedaley, 2016).

5. Conclusion

Smallholder farmers in Ethiopia have profound knowledge gaps regarding mycotoxins: 91.7% have never heard of aflatoxins or fumonisins, 95% are unaware of the associated health risks, and all attribute mould solely to storage pests. This misunderstanding drives hazardous practices, namely the universal use of subjective maturity tests, delayed harvest by more than half of farmers, manual threshing by four-fifths of farmers, no drying by three quarters of farmers, and storage in porous structures by nine-tenths of farmers. Insecticide use (86.7%) fails because surviving insects in porous structures produce metabolic water, raising humidity and promoting fungal growth.

Consequently, kernel infection increases from 87.2% at harvest to 99.1% in market samples, with *Fusarium* dominating (up to 91%) and *Aspergillus* reaching 46% in some markets. Seed germination collapses from 82% to 46%, resulting in approximately 36% loss, and vigour index becomes immeasurable, forcing farmers to use higher seeding rates or expensive certified seed, which perpetuates low productivity. The visual evidence from the blotter method confirms that fungal colonization directly prevents germination. The dominance of mycotoxin-producing fungi and the rewetting of grain (moisture rising from 12.0% to 13.2%) create ideal conditions for fumonisin and aflatoxin accumulation, posing direct risks to public health, trade and food security.

Integrated interventions are urgently needed: promote tolerant varieties (BH 540, BH 661) alongside the widely cultivated 'Limu'; subsidize hermetic storage (PICS bags, metal silos); provide low-cost moisture meters for objective harvest timing and drying to $\leq 13\%$ moisture; and deliver systematic farmer education distinguishing insects from fungi as causes of grain deterioration. Policy makers must establish national mycotoxin limits, integrate mycotoxin awareness into school curricula and extension programmes, and invest in post-harvest infrastructure. Without these actions, the cycle of fungal proliferation, seed viability loss and mycotoxin contamination will remain a critical barrier to safe and sustainable maize production in Ethiopia.

Consent

Written informed consent was obtained from all participating farmers after explaining the purpose of the study, the voluntary nature of participation, and the confidentiality of their responses. For illiterate participants, verbal consent was witnessed and documented by an independent local guide.

Ethical Approval

Prior to the survey, ethical approval was obtained from the Institutional Review Board (IRB) of Haramaya University.

Disclaimer (Artificial Intelligence)

Author(s) hereby declare that NO generative AI technologies such as Large Language Models (ChatGPT, COPILOT, etc) and text-to-image generators have been used during writing or editing of this manuscript.

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Competing Interests

Authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

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